

Updated Concept of the Persistent Identifier (PID) Services Working Group in the NFDI Section “Common Infrastructures”

Name of the working group

Persistent Identifier Services

Acronym

infra-pid

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Abstract

The following concept is an update of the concept published in 2022 by the PID (Persistent Identifier) Services working group within the NFDI Section “Common Infrastructures”.¹ The working group consists of representatives of existing PID services and as well as representatives from infrastructures using PIDs and who are already involved in various domain-specific consortia. The aim of the working group is to support the development of a PID service for the NFDI. The group is intended to serve as a forum to ensure the exchange between the emerging PID Coordination Hub, which is being developed by the PID4NFDI basic service project, and the NFDI consortia. Members of the working group can provide valuable input for service development, communicate needs from the consortia, and highlight best practices already in use for PID management. Resulting solutions should enable FAIR research workflows balancing out generic metadata requirements for PIDs that maximise resource discoverability on the one hand and subject-specific needs on the other. At the technical level, the partners want to realise interoperability between PID types and established systems and build on a high level of maturity here.

Motivation and Objectives

In recent years, the use of persistent identifiers (PIDs) to identify data objects, general research outputs, or the researchers themselves has been widely accepted in the scientific community. Every existing and every proposed NFDI consortium uses one or more PID systems in its everyday handling of research objects. Furthermore, reliable PID systems are the backbone for many additional services, like knowledge graphs or portfolio analytics services. Thus, persistent identifiers are by definition a fundamental building block of research data management and a mandatory element of FAIR data infrastructures.

Globally operating organisations and consortia like [DataCite](#), the [DOI foundation](#), or the [ePIC](#) consortium already offer trustworthy, mature, and well established infrastructures that are used for research data identification by almost all NFDI consortia. Furthermore, systems for the persistent identification of individual entities such as persons, organisations, places, events, or for general terms (like [ORCID](#), [ROR](#), [GND](#), or [VIAF](#)) are well established. Nevertheless, the assignment of identifiers in all NFDI consortia at the moment is scattered and heterogeneous in terms of actors, services, scope, quality, and costs involved. Having the core function of PIDs in RDM in mind, it is essential to analyse existing gaps and develop joint solutions in order to serve the needs of the individual communities and the NFDI as a whole. The preliminary work of the working group and the landscape analysis conducted by PID4NFDI have shown that the current practices of PID management in the consortia are highly heterogeneous.² The reasons for this are diverse and depend, among other factors, on the specific discipline and its awareness of the added value of PIDs and its data-sharing

¹ Bingert, S., Brase, J., Burger, F., Dreyer, B., Hagemann-Wilholt, S., Vierkant, P., & Wieder, P. (2022). Concept for Setting up the Persistent Identifier Services Working Group in the NFDI Section "Common Infrastructures" (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6507760>.

² El-Gebali, S., & Böhm, J. (2025). Landscape Analysis of PID Practices in NFDI (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652295>; Hagemann-Wilholt, S. (2023, February 13). PID4NFDI: Survey on PID Practices. Main results. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7635791>.

culture, the software used, the entities to be referenced with PIDs, available resources, the maturity of the infrastructure, etc. The work program of PID4NFDI aims to address challenges arising from these factors, e.g. different levels of adoption leading to a lack of interoperability according to metadata exchange options; or difficulties to finance access to PID provider services on an ad hoc basis for smaller organizations. However, efficient implementation requires close collaboration with the consortia to develop targeted service offerings.

This implies finding answers to questions like: How can the existing infrastructure of PID services be optimally used and interoperability with global research infrastructures like EOSC be ensured? What interfaces and licenses are needed? Which specific needs of consortia should be addressed? Where are central solutions - e.g. for support and training - needed?

Benefits to the NFDI

All stakeholders in the NFDI benefit from the use of PIDs in the research life cycle for unique identification of research resources, persons, institutions, projects, grants, outputs etc. Their use enables more accurate, richer and more standardised metadata. Thus, researchers and research institutions benefit as producers and users of research output from improved discoverability and interoperability of research data. Funding organisations and publishers find support in selecting and recognizing reviewers. PIDs promote compliance with e.g. Open Access or Data Management Plan policies. They reduce the administrative overhead of metadata ingestion and the communication for all stakeholders by reducing the amount of manual metadata entries in communications systems (publication, reporting, project databases etc.) and provide more current metadata. Metadata entry errors are reduced through automated processes and metadata is validated through authorization and linking of metadata. Standardised and complete metadata is the key to the acceptance and success of PID services which can be improved through training and education on the benefits that fair and meaningful data management can provide. Services like the PID Graph - developed by the EU funded project [FREYA](#) - that aggregates information from PID metadata further increases the benefits and potentials described above by linking and contextualising information about research output, researchers, their institutions etc.. It can provide insights into the benefits of NFDI as a whole for the German research landscape and in international comparison.

Figure 1: Benefits of PIDs in the research life cycle

This Figure including description is based on Brown, J. et al. (2021). The PID-optimised Research Lifecycle. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4991733>.

Processes of PID integration in research life cycle:

1. Grant Application and Review: Researchers and institutions pass PIDs for previous grants, outputs, organisations, people and projects to grant application systems. Funders ingest data about grants, outputs, organisations and projects from PID registries.
2. Grants Award: Funder register DOIs for new grants and associated metadata. Institutions ingest data about grants and associated people and organisations.
3. Project registration: Institutions register RAiDs and ePIC for projects and/update links to associated grants, equipment, people and organisations.
4. Output submission and publication: Researchers share their ORCID iD when submitting new outputs and connect ROR for institutional affiliations and grant DOIs for funding. Publisher/repository ingests data about grants, people, projects, and organisations linked to outputs.
5. Output registration: Publisher/repository register DOIs for new outputs and populates metadata.
6. Content notifications: PID registries send automatic updates of new publications etc. to creators, institutions and funders.
7. Reporting: Researchers and institutions pass PIDs for outputs, organisations, people and projects to funders reporting systems.

Objectives and Results of Work Plan 2024

The objectives set in the initial concept by the Working Group have been incorporated into the work program (2024)³ of the PID4NFDI project which emerged from the Working Group, for the development of a PID base service in the NFDI:

1. Understand NFDI PID use cases within domain specific consortia
2. Develop NFDI-wide concepts for the practical implementation of identified PID Systems
3. Disseminate knowledge to support implementation and usage of PID service(s)
4. Develop NFDI PID governance and licensing models
5. Collaborate with national & international stakeholder on PID related topics

PID4NFDI, with the support of use case partners from the NFDI consortia represented in the Working Group, has developed materials to map the PID landscape in the NFDI, analyze requirements, and define further steps for integrating PID solutions. During the project's initialization phase, the following materials were created:⁴

1. Landscape analysis and use case requirements
 - D1.1 Landscape of PID Practices within NFDI Services:
 - Survey Report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652295>
 - Survey Question Catalog: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14327774>
 - D1.2 + D2.1 Requirement Analysis of Selected Use Cases and Mapping to PID Providers:
 - NFDI4Microbiota – StrainInfo (DataCite): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14357800>
 - FAIRagro – GBIS repository (DataCite): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14506202>
 - Text+ – SUB Göttingen (GWDG): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14327691>
 - KonsortSWD – PID Service (GWDG): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14327770>
 - provided by KonsortSWD: Advantages of Participating in BASE4NFDI Projects - Spotlight on PID4NFDI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14289622>
2. Concepts for Interoperability:
 - D2.2 Catalog of Metadata Standards Relevant to NFDI:
 - Background Information: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14512768>
 - [Catalog as living document](#)
 - D2.3 + D2.4 Concepts for metadata interoperability, harmonization and technical integration of PID infrastructure: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14506138>
3. Training concepts and material to disseminate knowledge:
 - D3.1 Cookbook for getting started with PIDs (living document): <https://pid4nfdi-training.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>
 - D3.2 Training Concept: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14267399>

³ Bertelmann, R., Buys, M., Sens, I., Wieder, P., Bingert, S., Dreyer, B., Hagemann-Wilholt, S., Schrader, A. C., Stathis, K., Vierkant, P., & PID4NFDI Working Group. (2024). PID4NFDI – Persistent Identifier Services for the German National Research Data Infrastructure: Proposal for the Initialisation Phase of Base4NFDI. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281250>.

⁴ PID4NFDI publication overview: <http://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/publication>; Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/pid4nfdi/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>.

4. PID usage and integration and NFDI governance
 - D4.1 Overview of PID Providers and Types as [living document](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14328204) with background information: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14328204>
 - D4.2 Concept for Sustainable PID Registration Workflows: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14267446>
5. Base for provision of information and further collaborations:
 - D5.1 Communication Strategy: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14267462>
 - D5.2 Project Website: <http://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/>
 - D5.3 Stakeholder Workshop (Report): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14232461>.

Work Plan

The results from the initialization phase of PID4NFDI have been incorporated into the work program for the integration phase, with a more specialized focus on embedding and linking PIDs throughout the research data lifecycle. This approach aims to maximize the benefit and impact of each individual PID. Building on the initial concept, the objectives have been further refined to develop a comprehensive work program for integrating PIDs into the NFDI:

1. Develop a comprehensive strategy for selection, integration, and governance of PIDs across RD lifecycle – ensuring early adoption, proper usage, and alignment with NFDI requirements.
2. Enhance metadata quality and interoperability across NFDI infrastructure service by addressing gaps, establishing best practices – with focus on key use cases: instruments, samples, granular entities, projects and awards.
3. Ease access to and usage of PID services through technical advancements.
4. Establish a modular training service for diverse user groups, leveraging existing and developing new materials to foster PID awareness, adoption and integration.
5. Maximize impact of PID4NFDI outputs by coordinated outreach measures; foster community engagement and support other WPs in reaching target groups.

Ongoing feedback from the members of the Working Group, representing the user community, remains essential. The following sections outline the specific roles of Working Group members within the project's various work packages of PID4NFDI:

Table 1: PID4NFDI work plan for integration phase

WP	PID4NFDI Tasks in Integration Phase	Contribution of PID WG
1	Integration Strategy and Governance 1.1 Set up RD lifecycle-orientated focus groups 1.2 Develop a PID Selection Framework 1.3 Develop NFDI-wide PID Guidelines 1.4 Ensure connectivity to EOSC	Use case representatives participate in focus group workshops to articulate their needs for a lifecycle-oriented integration of PIDs and to share experiences and best practices with other participants for efficient distribution of knowledge among NFDI consortia.

2	<p>Enhancing Metadata Quality and Interoperability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1 Metadata quality assessment and gap analysis 2.2 Develop best practices and guidelines 2.3 Tools for metadata assessment and monitoring 2.4 Promoting integration and interoperability 2.5 Specific focus on material samples and research instruments: Monitoring and guidance 2.6 Explore metadata requirements for projects and facility usage awards 	<p>Use case partners provide insights into their metadata practices, identify challenges in improving and ensuring metadata quality, and contribute to documenting best practices.</p>
3	<p>Technical Implementation of Services in the Coordination Hub</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1 PIDs for research instruments: Advancing the infrastructure 3.2 Prefix registration service 3.3 Technical integration of the services 	<p>Use case partners support the exemplary integration and testing of developed service components.</p>
4	<p>Support and Training</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4.1 Collect and evaluate training material, identify gaps 4.2 Develop material to fill the gaps 4.3 Testing of material as feedback loop 4.4 Integration of developed material in PID Coordination Hub and NFDI training material infrastructure/collection 	<p>Members support PID4NFDI in identifying gaps in existing training materials and are willing to test newly developed resources.</p>
5	<p>Outreach and Community Engagement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5.1 Expand project website as entry point to Coordination Hub and communication channels 5.2 Determining stakeholder needs 5.3 Community engagement and facilitation of outreach events 5.4 Outputs management and curation 	<p>Members of the Working Group support networking with stakeholders from the NFDI consortia and other committees within and beyond the NFDI.</p>

Collaboration Plan

To successfully achieve the goals of the next project phase and advance the integration of PIDs into NFDI infrastructure services, PID4NFDI seeks collaboration with partners from the NFDI. Some of these partners are actively engaged in the working group, other NFDI stakeholder groups and also serve as key multipliers, helping to promote both discipline- and method-specific solutions, as well as cross-disciplinary approaches. These collaboration plans are outlined in the PID4NFDI work program and will be further developed in coordination with the working group members.

Table 2: Required support from NFDI sections and base services

Support from	Support
Base4NFDI: DMP4NFDI service	on identifying best practices on PIDs in DMP integration throughout research data lifecycle; providing contact to DMP providers within NFDI
Base4NFDI IAM4NFDI service	on registration of new types and PID service providers will require authentication through the NFDI AAI solution developed by IAM4NFDI, enabling group-specific entries in DTR and domain-specific profiles.
Section (Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance	on organising exchange with working groups on: Cookbooks, Guidance & Best Practice, TS, Search & Harvesting
Section Common Infrastructure (incl. ELN WG)	in setting up focus groups on ELNs and DMPs (recruitment from respective working groups, base service, and beyond)
Section Training & Education	in collecting and evaluating training material and exchange with other training groups
Section Industry Engagement	for exchange with companies providing commercial solutions for use cases (instrument manufacturers, inventory systems, ELN providers)

Specific infrastructure services will support PID4NFDI efforts by sharing insights into their current PID practices, participating in focus groups and workshops, and providing feedback on developed tools, solutions, and materials.

Table 3: Contributions from consortia and further partners

Consortium	Description of contribution from consortia: Providing insights on
KonsortSWD	Use case 'highly granular entities' according to elements within datasets and audio-visual materials
Daphne4NFDI	Use cases 'instruments', 'material samples', 'highly granular entities', 'facility usage awards'
CAU Kiel	Use case 'material samples' within different NFDI consortia and on cross-consortia / institutional integration of PIDs
NFDI4Objects	Use case 'material samples'
NFDI4Ing	PID integration in DMPs, use case 'highly granular data' and interoperability of PID systems
NFDI4Earth	Use of Instrument Identifier for the Sensor Management System delivering requirements for the service
NFDI4Cat	Use case 'highly granular data' and metadata schema requirements
RSpace	ELNs in Life Sciences

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC⁵) is an integrated infrastructure to create a web of FAIR data⁶. The development of EOSC is a significant and ongoing multi-stakeholder initiative with a large number of associated projects that build services integrated into the overall EOSC landscape. The EOSC Persistent Identifier (PID) policy¹ establishes service and infrastructure requirements for potential services providers. Also, the PID technical architecture document³ presents guidelines on the implementation of compliant PIDs and related services with PID EOSC Policy. It also identifies opportunities for interoperability between PID services and the EOSC framework. In this sense, these policy-related and technical guidelines shape the high-level aligning of PID4NFDI with EOSC. Example projects contributing to PID services for ESOC are FREYA, which built innovative PID-related services as a building block for EOSC, DICE, which offers i.e. handle-based PID services for European researchers, and the upcoming FAIRCORE4EOSC project, which will develop i.e. a PID graph, metadata schemata, and a PID registry. Within all projects, PID4NFDI partners are contributing to the European service development as well as to international initiatives such as the Research Data Alliance (RDA).

The format of the working group will be used in the future to offer a consultation hour on PID-related topics for the NFDI community during the meetings. Meetings will be held monthly, with questions collected in advance to cluster specific topics. The format will also provide an opportunity to present individual developments and analyses from the NFDI consortia. A contact form will be integrated into PID Coordination Hub.⁷

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⁵ Ferguson, Christine, McEntrye, Jo, Bunakov, Vasily, Lambert, Simon, Sandt, Stephanie van de, Kotarski, Rachael, Stewart, Sarah, MacEwan, Andrew, Fenner, Martin, Cruse, Patricia, Horik, René van, Dohna, Tina, Koop-Jacobsen, Ketil, Schindler, Uwe, & McCafferty, Siobhan. (2018). D3.1 Survey of Current PID Services Landscape (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1324296>.

⁶ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Schwarzmann, U., Fenner, M., Hellström, M., et al., PID architecture for the EOSC: report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group (WG) Architecture PID Task Force (TF), Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/525581>.

⁷ <http://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/>.

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